

////////////////////////////////////

THE APPROACH OF PRODUCT IDENTITY IN 3C BRANDS IN TAIWAN

Wen-Chih Chang / I-Wen Chen

Graduate School of Design, National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, Taiwan /
Graduate School of Design, National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, Taiwan
chenoften@yahoo.com.tw

ABSTRACT

Many globally successful brands use product identity to improve their brand recognition and to achieve the goal of differentiating themselves from their competitors. The researchers conducted in-depth interviews to investigate how five 3C international brands from Taiwan managed their product identity; the Ground Theory Method (GTM) was used to conduct data analysis. The results of the study can be used by 3C brands as a reference when designing their products. The main findings of this study include the following: (1) Product identity is built using brand objectives as a starting point; products are discriminated based on the products' constant and unique designs; (2) The more products a brand produces, the less likely these products are to share a common product identity; (3) A product's trademark and style are two of the most commonly used devices to reflect product identity and can be used across all types of products; and (4) There are six key factors that influence product identity.

Keywords: Product identity, Product style, Product design

INTRODUCTION

The information technology (IT) sector is currently the most robust industry in Taiwan. The proliferation rate of many information and communication technology (ICT) products produced here is the highest in the world and Taiwan also serves as the largest ICT manufacturer and provider in the world. In recent years, the IT industry has expanded to include electronic high-tech industries involving computers, communication, and consumer electronics, which are collectively known as 3C.

Product identity is a basic principle in boosting a company or brand recognition and to maintain consistency across markets and products (Karjalainen, 2001). As is evident in successful brands across the globe, that consumers can identify brands based on the characteristics of products. For instance, German brands Mercedes-Benz and BMW use the family symbolism unique to these two brands to encourage consumers to perceive the brand value based on the external appearance of products. Past studies on product identity focused mainly on consumer viewpoints. This study, on the other hand, views the issue from the perspective of how brands assert their product identity. The researchers investigated 3C brands in Taiwan and conducted in-depth interviews with designers in these companies to gain better insight on how product identity is asserted through 3C brands. The results of the study can fill the gap that currently exists in product identity related studies and can be also used as reference for the creation of product identity among 3C brands. This study mainly investigates: (1) how product identity is formed in 3C brands; (2) how product identity is shared across different product types when a brand produces diverse products; and (3) what key factors influence 3C brand product identity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

IDENTITY AND BRAND IDENTITY

Identity comprises minds and visuals, and products are a representation of visual identity (Wu, 1991; Lin, 1990). The outward expression of a brand, including its name, trademark, communications, and visual appearance. Because the identity is assembled by the brand owner, it reflects how the owner wants the consumer to perceive the brand. Brand identity

is fundamental to consumer recognition and symbolizes the brand's differentiation from competitors. In the realm of brand identity, core identity is the most important factor and does not change even as the brand extends its reach to new markets and products. Products are a core consideration when developing core identity (Aaker and Joachimsthaler, 2000). Therefore, product identity can be considered a significant part while one brand focuses on its brand identity development.

PRODUCT IDENTITY (PI)

Product identity (PI) comprises aesthetics, images, and semantics, combining both tangible and intangible elements such as explicit design cues and implicit design cues. Explicit cues refer to design characteristics and methods that can be directly identified and perceived, whereas implicit cues are tacitly perceived (Karjalainen, 2001, 2003, 2007). PI is a standard that maintains the consistency of a product's image and effectively transmit information as intended by companies and thus plays an important communication role between the maker and user. The main purpose of PI is to ensure consistency, form an identity, and to deliver a product image. Products differentiate themselves from their competitors by featuring unique functions and designs (Koh and Lee, 2007; Chang, Yu and Chen, 2009). For example, to ensure consistency between product concept and brand objectives, BRAUN struck a compromise between these competing interests. By using a product to develop brand image, BRAUN has become synonymous with their product style (Lin, 2003).

It is evident from the above discussion that products are the most direct part of contact between a brand and their consumers. Products are a component of visual identity, as well as being an indispensable facet of a brand's core identity. A brand must therefore take PI into consideration when establishing its identity system. PI involves both an explicit and tangible portion and an implicit and intangible portion. These components can be presented through *product style*, *product image* and *product semantics*.

PERFORMANCE OF PRODUCT IDENTITY (PI)

Product style can be directly perceived through the product. A style is developed when a set of characteristics appears repeatedly on a series of products. When a set of characteristics recur in products created by an individual, this can be described as an individual style; alternatively, when a set of characteristics recur in products created by a group, this can be described as a group style. External factors that develop product style and compose product identity include the following: the product form, design style, decorative level, pattern and detail treatments, functions, quality and structure, materials, texture, colors, uniqueness, trademark arrangement, mode of operation, and special techniques (Chan, 2000; Dawson, Larsen, Cawood and Lewis, 2005; Chang, Yu and Chen, 2009). *Product image* is comprised of form, texture, colors, and other factors. People develop intuitive associations toward the image of the product through the interaction of these factors. The most evident of these associations is the images generated in visual part. These product features generate intuitive associations and become connected to the life experiences and cultural backgrounds of its users. The company, the designers, and the users all contribute to the development of product images and these three factors correlate with one another (Oh, Lee, and Kim, 2009; Tseng, 2006). *Product semantics* is the study of the meaning behind products. Its main purpose is to allow products to prove themselves, to build meaning in the products, and to identify the unique qualities of products (Krippendorff, 1989; Butter, 1987). Warell and Nabo (2002) suggested that it is necessary to ensure that a product is delivering a consistent message during product development. This way, when the company releases new prototypes or new generations of the product, consumers can identify the new product as being produced by the same company. Bürdek (1991) indicated that product semantics mainly comprise symbols, aesthetics, and indications. Symbols refer to the consideration of the physical, psychological, habitual, historical, social, and cultural facets of users in product design; aesthetics refer to the aesthetic contributions of the product appearance; and indications refer to the visual representation of product functions, with the

main focus being the use and operation of the product.

Desmet and Hekkert (2007) classified product experience into three levels: aesthetic experience, experience of meaning, and emotional experience. Aesthetic experience is concerned with a product's ability to create positive emotions in the user and is mainly focused on the visual aspect; experience of meaning is concerned with the meaning we attach to products and is mainly focused on the individualized and symbolic aspects of a product and is related to semantic interpretation; and emotional experience is concerned with the emotions induced by a product. Based on the above discussion, this study suggests that the presentation of PI is involved in four divisions, namely: product appearance, product contents, product semantics, and product emotions. (1) product appearance: product style is made consistent by designing products based in a common appearance and is considered a tangible feature, e.g. ALESSI's products present strong and unique design style; (2) product contents: product image is made consistent by ensuring that products are delivering a consistent message and is considered an intangible feature, e.g. MUJI's products present concept of environmental protection; (3) product semantics: product semantics are composed of symbols (i.e. product content), aesthetics (i.e. product appearance), and indications (the visual representation of functions) and are characterized as both tangible and intangible, e.g. product design of PHILIPS often use clear associations to make form follow meaning; and (4) product emotions: this involves the inducing of consistent emotions from the users and is considered an intangible feature, e.g. VOLVO's products always induce people the feelings of characteristically safe, Scandinavian and dynamic.

METHODS

This study used qualitative methods, namely in-depth interviews, to collect the required data. The researchers conducted interviews with five successful 3C international brands in Taiwan and used the Ground Theory Method (GTM) to analyze the interview data to determine how brands implement PI. The following section describes the research methods employed in this study.

SELECTION OF BRANDS AND PARTICIPANTS

The researchers first selected eight 3C brands from twenty brands with the best brand value in Taiwan. Afterwards, eight designers in the industry (all of which have more than 3 years' experience in product design and design 3C products) were asked to recommend brands with good PI among the eight 3C brands. Five out of eight of the brands (denoted by A, B, C, D, and E) were recommended by at least four designers.

In-depth interviews were then conducted with industrial designers (denoted by a, b, c, d, and e) from five different companies. The participants were chosen by the members of the brand design department and have: (1) at least three years' experience in product design with the brand; (2) experience implementing PI; and (3) familiarity with the application of the brand's PI. Brand and participant data see Table 1.

Brand Code	A	B	C	D	E
Company Founded	1976	1989	1984	1997	1986
Brand Development ⁽¹⁾	1987	1989	2001	2006	2009
Capital ⁽²⁾	280	370	38.55	75.54	106.9
2010 Brand Value ⁽³⁾	14.01	12.85	N/A	13.71	N/A
Participant Code	a	b	c	d	e
Position	ID	ID	Design Chief	ID	Senior Manager
Design Experience	4 years	5 years	11 years	5 years	23 years

Table 1. Brand and Participant Data (Note 1: brand development refers to the period when a company began to focus on brand management and should not be confused with the establishment of the brand. Note 2: a unit of capital is per hundred million NT dollars. Note 3: a unit of brand value is per hundred million US dollars.)

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEWS

This study implemented semi-structured interviews and asked more detailed questions after participants answering every single question to obtain more information. The interview questions were checked for face validity before being sent to the participants a week before the formal interview session; related literature on PI was also included. This allowed the participants to reflect on the questions and formulate opinions to ensure the completeness of

their responses. The interviews were conducted in the meeting room or visitor's lounge in the participants' companies. More explanations were given prior to the actual interview. Pictures of all the products in the brand were provided in the interview to facilitate explanation. A camera and a digital recorder were also used to record the interviews.

DATA ANALYSIS AND QUALITY INSPECTION

The interview data was analyzed using the GTM. The method comprises two steps: (1) The recorded interviews were transcribed and the participants were requested to verify the accuracy of the transcription; further interviews were conducted when any points were unclear and (2) two researchers assigned coding to the transcription; data identified in the coding phase were then classified, simplified, analyzed, and concluded. This study employed two methods to ensure the quality of data analysis: (1) The participants were requested to view the transcription and the analysis to ensure the accuracy of the information and the interpretation and (2) the two researchers analyzed the data together and shared information regarding their analysis to ensure that each understood what the other was working on to avoid errors and omissions and as well as maintain consistency in data analysis. During the coding process, the researchers checked the transcription constantly and checked the coding twice at nearly two weeks interval to avoid inaccuracies and ensure the consistency of data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PI IN TAIWAN 3C BRANDS

It is evident from the interviews that there are three main reasons why 3C brands implement PI: (1) to deliver brand or product information, such as brand concepts and the overall impression the product hopes to make; (2) to ensure the consistency between the image project by products and the brand itself in the long run; and (3) to facilitate product identification and to differentiate the brand from its competitors.

The five brands investigated in this study had clear brand objectives. Their PIs are developed based on

these brand objectives using such approaches as trademarks (TR), product style management (PSM), forms (F), colors (C), texture (T), and quality maintenance and technological breakthroughs (QMTB). Table 2 explains approaches of PI in 3C brands.

Approaches of PI		Descriptions
Trade-mark (TR)	Trademark Arrangement	Trademark arrangement to identify brand
	Trademark Size and Position	Regulates the size and positioning of the trademark
	[Unique Trademark Effects]	The use of a trademark with special decorations or light design
Product Style Management (PSM)		Controlling Products project a consistent image
Form (F)	Consistent Form	Consistent product appearance
	Consistent Controls and Positioning of Operating Area	The operating area of products are kept consistent controls and positioning
	[Local Characteristics]	The products are held some obviously local characteristics
Colors (C)	Same Basic and Accompanying Colors	The use of the same basic and accompanying colors
	[Unique Color Representation]	The use of special colors or decorating products using color belts
Texture (TE)	Consistent Detail and Surface Treatments	The products are kept the consistency of detail and surface treatments
	[Unique Surface Treatments]	The products are treated with a special surface treatments
	[Unique Materials]	The use of materials less common in 3C products, e.g., leather, bamboo, or ceramics
[Quality Maintenance and Technological Breakthroughs] (QMTB)		Product size limitations and processing technology breakthroughs

Table 2. Approaches of PI in 3C brands (Note: [] refers to product identification through the uniqueness of appearance and the rest refers to product identification through the consistency of appearance)

Brand Code		A	B	C	D	E
Duration of Brand Development (years)		24	22	10	5	2
Brand Capital Ranking		2	1	5	4	3
2010 Brand Value Ranking		1	3	N/A	2	N/A
Brand Objectives		*	*	*	*	*
T R	Trademark Arrangement	*	*	*	*	*
	Trademark Size and Position	*	*	*	*	*
	[Unique Trademark Effects]	*				*
Product Style Management		*	*	*	*	
F	Consistent Form		*		*	*
	Consistent Controls and Positioning of Operating Area		*		*	
	[Local Characteristics]	*		*	*	
C	Same Basic and Accompanying Colors		*		*	
	[Unique Color Representation]	*		*		
T E	Consistent Detail and Surface Treatments		*		*	
	[Unique Surface Treatments]		*		*	
	[Unique Materials]		*		*	
[Quality Maintenance and Technological Breakthroughs]		*	*		*	

Table 3. Summary of PI implementation in each 3C brand

Table 3 summarizes PI implementation in each 3C brand in the study and several findings can be noticed here.

- 3C brands in Taiwan mainly use trademarks, product style management, and form to show PI. All of the brands included in this study identify their products through trademark arrangement and the uniform size and positioning of the trademark; four of those brands identify their products through product style management (Brands A, B, C, and D); and three of those brands identify their products through a consistent form (Brands B, D, and E) and local characteristics (Brands A, C, and D).
- Brand E had been developing its brand for the shortest time among all those interviewed, as all others interviewed have been conducting brand development for over 5 years and have established their product style. These findings show that trademark arrangement is the most important PI strategy implemented by 3C brands

in Taiwan in their initial stages; product style management, on the other hand, is only used for PI in 3C brands after a period of time from establishment.

- Brands A, B, and D have the best brand value in Taiwan. The three brands are secure in their current positions and emphasize superior product sizes and advanced processing technologies. This suggests that imposing quality maintenance and technological breakthroughs are part of implementing PI in leading brands. This is because leading brands are better equipped to implement quality maintenance and technological breakthroughs and consumers are more willing to welcome new introductions from these brands.
- Taiwan’s 3C brands differentiate themselves by adhering to a consistent and unique product appearance for two reasons: (1) a consistent appearance can be used to extend the range of the brand through their products’ family characteristics; this effect, however, is limited to consumers who are familiar with the brand and (2) 3C products are inherently innovative and diverse; thus, a unique appearance can make a product more visually attractive as well as differentiating it from its competitors.
- Overall, Brands B and D are two brands with the best PI in Taiwan. These two brands have clear specifications for maintaining the consistent appearance of their products through the use of trademark arrangement, trademark size and positioning, consistent controls and positioning of operating area, same basic and accompanying colors, consistent detail and surface treatments, and quality maintenance and technological breakthroughs

PI ACROSS DIFFERENT PRODUCTS

All of the participants indicated that, “PI is implemented differently across different product types. This is because the focus of product design is different from the direction of the product. It is thus hard to use entirely identical PIs across different product types.” Five product types were discussed in the interview by participants, namely: mobile phones, digital cameras, projectors, monitors, and laptops.

Among the five brands investigated, only Brands B, C, and E implemented PI for at least two product types and are considered multi-product type brand.

Figure 1. PI of multiple product types (Note: [] refers to product identification through the uniqueness of appearance and the rest refers to product identification through the consistency of appearance.).

Figure 1 illustrates the PI of multiple product types. The intersecting region in the figure 1 (gray area) refers to the PI used across product types. The results showed that more product types there are, the fewer PIs are shared across product types. For example, Brand B implemented PI on two products (laptops and mobile phones) and shared six PIs (TR1, TR2, PSM, F1, F2, and TE1) across these two product types. Brand C implemented PI on five products (cameras, mobile phones, projectors, monitors, and laptops) and shared three PIs (TR1, TR2, and PSM) across these five product types. Furthermore, PIs shared across product types pertain to the consistency of appearance; the most commonly used PIs range include trademark arrangement (TR1), trademark size and position (TR2), and product style management (PSM); Brand C for example, TR1, TR2, and PSM are shared across 5 product types.

KEY FACTORS INFLUENCING PI

There are six key factors influencing PI, namely: brand objectives; brand image and direction; product type, positioning, and attributes; trends and social issues; new technologies and materials; and advertisements. There first five key factors, which are brand objectives, brand image and direction, product type, positioning, and attributes, trends and social issues, and new technologies and materials, influence PI formation; the last factor which is advertisements influence PI performance.

1. Brand Objectives: brand objectives are similar to the constitution and penetrate the implementation of product design, influence product development, and could even change its design process and structure.
2. Brand Image and Direction: consumers show a higher acceptance rate towards brands with strong images and market appeal, thus encouraging these brands to become more innovative or impose stricter restrictions.
3. Product Type, Positioning, and Attribute: product types (such as mobile phones or computers), consumer groups (such as students or businessmen), and product attribute (such as business or home type and advanced or basic) influence product appearance and PI.

4. Trends and Social Issues: current trends influence the direction of brand development. Social issues also influence PI. For example, ecological concerns motivate brands to develop green designs, which are in turn reflected through PI.
5. New Technologies and Materials: new technologies and materials influence the performance of product appearance and in turn PI performance.
6. Advertisements: due to the immense number of products in the market, many consumers are unable to identify brands based on product appearance alone. Advertisements enhance consumers' impression of products belonging to which brand and at times inform the consumer directly of the product's features and thus improve product identity.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, six findings were drawn based on in-depth interviews conducted on five 3C international brands with PI. These findings are able to generally apply to PI studies and PI practices. That is, On one hand, the range of PI research can be complemented by the study, and on the other hand, the six findings can be used by 3C brands as a reference when designing their products:

1. The PI of 3C brands in Taiwan are developed based on brand objectives and are presented in the aspect of trademarks, product style management, forms, colors, textures, and quality maintenance and technological breakthroughs.
2. The main purpose of PI includes the delivery of information, maintaining a consistent image, and to facilitate identity and differentiation. To achieve these goals, 3C brands create products' family characteristics to maintain a consistent appearance and also present products in a unique manner to differentiate these from other products. Identifying family characteristics of a brand's products requires consumers to have an extensive knowledge and understanding of the product; and product uniqueness, on the other hand, it requires the application of commercials and advertisements to facilitate recognition.
3. The most commonly used PIs in 3C brands include trademark arrangement, trademark size and

position, and product style management. In the initial stages of 3C brand development, trademark arrangement is used to be main PI ; afterwards, a unique product style will gradually develop, and product style management is used as the PI for the 3C brand. Quality maintenance and technological breakthroughs are one of the PIs used by market leaders.

4. Different product types use different PIs. The more product types a brand has, the fewer PIs it will have that are shared across different product types. The most widely applied PI approaches include trademark arrangement, trademark size and position, and product style management.
5. There are five key factors influencing PI formation, namely: brand objectives; brand image and direction; product type, positioning, and attribute; trends and social issues; and new technologies and materials. Advertisements are the main factor influencing PI performance.
6. Overall, PI is not common in 3C brands in Taiwan. In the five brands investigated in this study, Brands B and D identify their products by showing their unique appearances but also present overall products' family characteristics through the use of forms, colors, and textures. These 3C brands currently employ the most comprehensive development of PI approaches in Taiwan.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D. A. and Joachimsthaler, E. (2000). *Brand Leadership: The Next Level of the Brand Revolution*. New York: Free Press.
- Bürdek, B. E. (1991). *Geschichte, Theorie und Praxis der Produktgestaltung*. Köln: DuMont Buchverlag.
- Butter, R. (1987). Product Semantics - A New Perspective on Function in Industrial Design. *Proceedings of the International UIAH'87 Conference*, University of Industrial Arts, Helsinki, 114-125
- Chan, C. S. (2000). Can style be Measured. *Design Studies*, 21(3), 277-291.
- Chang, W. C., Yu, C. J., and Chen, I. W. (2009). The Approach of Product Identity about Ceramic Brand Companies in Taiwan. *Proceedings of the International Association of Societies of Design Research 2009* [CD ROM], Seoul, Korea.
- Dawson, K., Larsen, P., Cawood, G., and Lewis, A. (2005). National Product Design Identities. *Journal compilation*, 14(4), 393-404.
- Desmet, P. M. A., and Hekkert, P. (2007). Framework of Product Experience. *International Journal of Design*, 1(1), 57-66.
- Karjalainen, T. M. (2001). When is a car like a drink? Metaphor as a means to distilling brand and product identity. *Design Management Journal*, 12(1), 66-71.

- Karjalainen, T. M. (2003). Semantic knowledge in the creation of brand-specific product design. *Proceedings of the 5th European Academy of Design Conference*, Barcelona, Spain, 1-12
- Karjalainen, T. M. (2007). It Looks Like a Toyota: Educational Approaches to Designing for Visual Brand Recognition. *International Journal of Design*, 1(1), 67-81.
- Koh, S. Y., and Lee, S. J. (2007). A Study on Iconic Element for Establishing Design Identity Strategy. *Proceedings of the International Association of Societies of Design Research 2007* [CD ROM], Hong Kong.
- Krippendorff, K. (1989). On the Essential Contexts of Artifacts or on the Proposition that Design Is Making Sense (of Things). *Design Issues*, 5(2), 9-39.
- Lin, M. H. (2003). *The Thoughts and Trends of Industrial Design*. Taipei: Chwa.
- Lin, P. S. (1990). *CIS*. Taipei: Yi-Fong-Tang.
- Oh, H., Lee, W., and Kim, M. S. (2009). A Study on an Effect of Olfactory Stimulation on Product Image by the Type of the Product. *Proceedings of the International Association of Societies of Design Research 2009* [CD ROM], Seoul, Korea.
- Tseng, L. J. (2006). *Cognitive Psychology*. Taipei: Wunan.
- Warell, A., and Nabo, M. (2002). Handling Product Identity and Form Development Issues in Design Management Using Design Format Modeling. *Proceedings of the 11th International Forum on Design Management Research and Education, Design Management Institute*, Northeastern University, Boston, 10-12.
- Wu, J. S. (1991). *CI and Exposition*. Taipei: New Image.